

The Spin System in Quantum Mechanics (Per Leonard Susskind)

As Susskind explains, a **spin system** can be thought of as a small physical system (like an electron), which has a **vector** associated with it. This vector points in some direction and has components along the x, y, and z axes. To measure the spin, we bring a detector (the "black box" in the video) and align it with the spin's polarization axis. When we press the "button" to measure, we get either +1 or -1—no intermediate values.

If the detector aligns with the spin's direction, we get +1 (spin-up) consistently. If we turn the detector, especially if it's perpendicular to the spin direction, the results become random. This randomness arises from quantum superposition, and the behavior is weird—but it's part of the core mystery of quantum mechanics.

Quantum Information Holography: A Step Further

In **QIH**, this setup is mirrored but extends to black holes and spacetime geometry. Let me explain how it works:

Step 1: The Quantum System and Measurement in QIH

In QIH, we still have a quantum state described by a vector $|\psi\rangle$, just like in Susskind's example. The state can be in a superposition of $|0\rangle$ (spin-up) and $|1\rangle$ (spin-down):

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle$$

But here's where QIH adds something new: the **Planck qubit** acts as the detector, and **Hawking radiation** serves as the "button" that collapses the wave function. When Hawking radiation interacts with the system, it forces the collapse, and we get $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$, just like measuring the spin in quantum mechanics.

The combined state of the system and the Planck qubit looks like this before measurement:

$$|q\rangle \otimes |\psi\rangle = (\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle) \otimes |q\rangle$$

Hawking radiation, emitted from the black hole, interacts with the Planck qubits and collapses the wave function, yielding outcomes with probabilities $|\alpha|^2$ and $|\beta|^2$. This process happens every **Planck time**, meaning that quantum states are continuously measured.

Step 2: Interference Patterns and Spin

Susskind explains how a spin system produces either +1 or -1, depending on the detector's alignment. The same thing happens in **QIH**, but the probabilities of these outcomes are tied to the **interference** between quantum state vectors. In QIH, the probability of getting +1 (spin-up) is:

$$P(\text{spin-up}) = \cos^2(\theta/2)$$

And the probability of getting -1 (spin-down) is:

$$P(\text{spin-down}) = \sin^2(\theta/2)$$

This matches what Susskind says about the quantum spin system. When the qubit's axis aligns with the quantum state vector, you get **constructive interference**, or $+1$. When it's 90° off (perpendicular), you get **destructive interference**, or random results. This is where the connection between quantum mechanics and the geometry of spacetime becomes clear: the alignment of vectors gives us information about spacetime's geometry and quantum states.

Step 3: Entanglement and Holography in Black Holes

In **QIH**, we go a step further by addressing the **black hole information paradox**. The qubits inside the black hole are **entangled** with their virtual particle counterparts on the **event horizon**. Here's where it gets really interesting: as a virtual particle falls into the black hole, it "bobs" up and down on the interference pattern—like a fishing bobber on a lake. Its entangled twin on the event horizon **mirrors** this movement, creating a holographic image of what's happening inside the black hole.

This reflection works like a **mirror**. The entangled particle outside the event horizon etches a holographic imprint of the particle inside the black hole. It's as if you're watching a movie of what's happening inside the black hole, projected onto the event horizon. The **Hawking radiation** interacting with these qubits acts as the key to this process, continuously collapsing the wave function and preserving the information holographically.

Step 4: Solving the Black Hole Information Paradox

Here's how we solve the paradox:

Each time **Hawking radiation** is emitted, the **angular frequency** ω of the radiation encodes information about the black hole's **mass**, **charge**, and **spin**. This information is imprinted on the Planck qubits on the event horizon. By analyzing the angular frequency of Hawking radiation at each Planck time, we can infer the properties of the black hole.

The angular frequency is related to the energy of the radiation by Planck's relation:

$$E = \hbar\omega$$

From this, we can deduce the mass of the black hole. Similarly, the spin and charge are encoded in the angular frequency and the orientation of the quantum state vector. This entire process ensures that information about the black hole's internal state is **holographically encoded** on the event horizon, ensuring that no information is lost—solving the black hole information paradox.

Step 5: Dual Description of General Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

The beauty of **QIH** is that it provides a **dual description** of both **quantum mechanics (QM)** and **general relativity (GR)**. The way quantum state vectors interfere (constructive vs. destructive interference) mirrors how spacetime geometry encodes information. This process ties together quantum mechanics and gravitational fields, showing how the structure of spacetime can be described through quantum information.

Conclusion

In **Quantum Information Holography**, we see how the **Planck qubit** acts as the detector, and **Hawking radiation** serves as the "button" that collapses the wave function at each Planck time. The entangled virtual particles on the event horizon mirror the motion of their counterparts inside the black hole, creating a holographic imprint of what's happening inside. This process encodes the black hole's mass, charge, and spin, allowing us to see what's happening inside the black hole as if watching a movie through a mirror.